

GREAT Case Study

Waterwise: Phase 1

Work Package: WP4: Case Study Waterwise

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

Scope: This document reports on the first GREAT case study cycle with sponsor Waterwise and can be considered phase 1 in that collaboration. Phase 2 and further dissemination activities will be reported on in subsequent documents.

Objective: Water security, essential to both human survival and societal infrastructure, is significantly influenced by everyday individual behaviours. Yet, in many parts of the world, the topic receives limited public attention. In collaboration with Waterwise, this case study investigates the use of the GREAT case study cycle developed from the MIR approach (Tobi & Kampen, 2018) to design and use playful dilemmas and interactive activities. The goal of this work is to support citizen discussions that educate, share knowledge, and co-construct meaning of sustainable water use.

Methods: Through case study workshops with Waterwise, three activities were developed for online water security discussions. A water perception and use survey, data exploration of supply and demand challenges, and a playful dilemma game. 25 participants took part in the initial implementation of these activities.

Key Findings: Participants showed greater understanding of their water footprint and supply and demand challenges faced within the UK. The designed activities fostered wide ranging discussions when used in small groups of strangers online. Some Individuals reported less water use and greater concern for their water use behaviour. Water use discussions covered a wide gamut of behaviour changes and potential supportive policies and mechanisms that could help reduce water waste within the home. However, knowledge deficit within areas meant that ideas generated were not viewed through the practical implementation. Technological barriers were identified when engaging in this approach on mobile devices.

Implications: Playful discussions can be an engaging and positive discussion space on sustainability practice online. Water system knowledge is low and affords an opportunity to educate and develop a vision of what water use looks like (water culture) but requires transparency on how the water industry supports this endeavour too. The designed approach could be used for online small-scale focus groups to engage with own water footprint and share knowledge on water security. Content could be adapted for a given social dilemma. However, time to make such content can be substantial.

2. Introduction

Waterwise (GCS2) is the second case study conducted within the EU Horizon-funded project GREAT (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (<https://www.greatproject.gg/>). This case study was conducted within the UK and led by the University of Greater Manchester. The case study sponsor, Waterwise, promotes the reduction of water waste across all aspects of society (citizen, industry, agriculture etc). Citizen engagement with less wasteful water habits is key to a societies' water security (BSI, 2024). In collaboration with this sponsor, the aim of this study was to investigate citizen preferences and attitudes in adopting more water efficient habits. Specifically, it sought to identify which water use habits people are most willing to change to reduce waste, and what supporting policies could help enable these shifts. These findings are intended to guide the development and communication of citizen water efficiency policy and effective strategies for encouraging the public to reduce water wastage.

To frame the significance of this case study, water security ensures access to fresh water for survival and sustainability (BSI, 2024). Sustaining water systems amid climate change and population growth is complex, requiring efficient water use across infrastructure, industries, and agriculture (He et al., 2021). Individual water habits significantly impact national reserves—for instance, daily water use in the USA is 379L per person and 149L in UK (BSI, 2024, p31-32). Water use is influenced by various factors, including local climate, cultural practices, recent weather conditions, pricing, and occupational needs. However, aligning societal water consumption with the geographic availability of freshwater resources is key to ensuring a sustainable supply.

The United Kingdom faces growing concerns over drought and long-term water security. Since 2004, four distinct drought periods have been documented: 2004–2006, 2010–2012, 2018, and most notably 2022, which marked one of the most severe droughts in half a century (Barker, 2024). Elevated summer temperatures continue to drive up demand, while prolonged dry spells diminish groundwater reserves. Excessive abstraction during such periods hampers the ability of aquifers to recover, thereby compounding water scarcity in subsequent years. Heightening these difficulties, water demand in the UK is rising, driven by population growth and increased consumption within the energy sector. Forecasts suggest that by 2050, England could face a shortfall of approximately five billion litres per day between water demand and sustainable supply (Environment Agency, 2024). In response, the UK government and water industry are advancing initiatives that include expanding reservoir capacity, investing in desalination technologies, adopting smart metering, promoting efficient appliances, and addressing leakage reduction. Crucially, public engagement through education and awareness is recognised as a key component of these efforts. An estimated 7% reduction in daily water use, equating to 160

million litres (Environment Agency, 2024). Beyond these savings, public awareness is key to fostering acceptance of future infrastructure reforms. Raising awareness about water conservation and exploring how citizens can be supported in less wasteful water use is crucial to the future water security of the UK.

To raise awareness of the current UK water conversation, simply providing information to the public is not enough. This one-way information approach assumes that all the public needs is more information to understand a given climate conversation and change behaviour accordingly (Simis *et al.*, 2016). However, engagement with a given climate conversation is shaped by personal beliefs, attitudes, and values. A two-way discussion facilitates integration of new information within these biases (Ettinger & Painter, 2023, Ettinger *et al.*, 2023). Within a group, discussion can help make sense collectively, see where different perspectives converge, and make collective judgments on how to respond (Pröpper, van Eck, & Bakker, 2024), reducing barriers to understanding and behaviour change. Creating safe spaces for information delivery and discussion fosters engagement with the topic at hand and provides an opportunity for information brokers to view a collectives' understanding, concerns, and solutions within a climate discussion.

The GCS2 case study requires an educational, small group discussion space for citizens to reflect and learn about water use and then express their attitudes and preferences to less wasteful behaviours and policies. These citizens may or may not know each other and so to structure these conversations a series of playful activities will be used. The goal of these activities will be to:

- 1) Improve public awareness of water supply within the UK
- 2) Improve public concern towards water use
- 3) Identify habits that citizens would be willing to change to reduce water waste in the home
- 4) Identify supporting policies and mechanisms to aid wating less water in the home

Educational games have demonstrated their capacity to support learning outcomes and engagement with a variety of topics (Hummel *et al.*, 2011; Hyde *et al.*, 2016.; Hwang & Chang, 2023). However, a tension exists between delivering subject depth and maintaining engaging gameplay. Situated between gamification and game-based learning, playful learning occupies a nuanced middle ground that integrates game elements into educational activities without requiring the structure of complete games (Plass *et al.*, 2020).

Building upon this foundation, the GCS2 case study within the GREAT project examines the utility of playful dilemma games and supporting activities in facilitating climate discussions among citizens within constrained timeframes. Recognising that opportunities for civic engagement with climate topics are often limited, this case study explores how structured, playful activities can create spaces for dialogue and reflection within one-hour sessions.

Although reduced time may limit the scope of deliberation, such an approach has the potential to lower barriers to entry and foster meaningful engagement.

This case study does not examine a specific water use policy but instead investigates citizen attitudes and preferences regarding acceptable daily water consumption and where they feel they need support to achieve sustainable water use. Engaging with lived experience and personal practice, the approach seeks to uncover the existing knowledge base among citizens and identify behavioural patterns that could be sensitively “nudged” toward reduction if needed. The study offers insight into how citizens perceive water sustainability and their role within it. For policymakers, this creates a valuable opportunity to observe authentic dialogue and deliberation around domestic water use. The findings may inform supportive strategies and guide the development of policy frameworks that keep in mind citizen perspectives

The overarching GREAT research questions explored in this study phase are:

- **RQ 1.1** Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens’ views on social dilemmas?
- **RQ 1.2** How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens’ views on social dilemmas?
- **RQ 1.3** How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens’ views on social dilemmas?
- **RQ 2.1** What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens’ views in relation to social dilemmas.
- **RQ 2.3** What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?

3. Methodology

3.1 Study Design

This case study uses mixed qualitative methods (Tobi & Kampen, 2018). Online discussions were fostered through playful activities design through the GREAT project cycle in collaboration with Waterwise (See figure 10 and section “**Detail the design process for the case study**” to see steps and development of these activities). The discussions describe citizen attitudes and preferences. Repeated measures were used to observe self-reporting of water use before and after these sessions. Through this approach, we collect data through discussion audio, reflective feedback, surveys, and activity text entry. The online format was used as it may encourage more participants to take part in the sessions across broader areas of the UK.

The activities were as follows:

- 1) Water use survey
- 2) Data exploration of supply and demand challenges
- 3) Playful dilemma game to collaboratively decide on citizen behaviour to save a city from drought
- 4) Reflective survey and discussion on session experience

Participants were then given a follow up survey one week later. This survey asked the same questions from activity one additional questions exploring any changes in water concern, discussion, or behaviour habits. All discussions were conducted online through a video conferencing tool, Zoom. Each small group discussion session took approximately one hour.

Participants would arrive online to the allocated Zoom session. The information sheet was discussed, and consent to take part was gathered (10 mins). Then followed facilitated activities. Activity one (10 mins), activity two (15 mins), and activity three (15 mins). A reflective survey was then given to explore participants experience of the session. During this reflective section, the text entry of what participants enjoyed the most and least appeared on screen to engage some final thoughts on this reflection (10 mins). One week later, a follow-up survey was sent to the participants, which asked the same questions from activity one, along with additional questions inquiring about any changes in behaviour.

Discussion activities were supported by the Dilemma Based Learning (DiBL), (DIBL, 2025) platform provided by the project partner, Serious Games Interactive (SGI). Through this platform, participants can vote, input text, and make choices on the facilitated presentation shown to them. The facilitator's screen will present core information to lead activities and discussions. The participants can see the facilitators screen and will also have a player's screen they can access through a webpage on a mobile device or desktop PC. Through the player's screen, participants can take part in surveys, vote, enter text, and make choices (see figure 1).

Figure 1. Screenshot from published work using the GCS2 playful activities (Watson, 2025). Discussion sessions were online. Participants viewed the facilitator’s screen through the Zoom video conferencing platform. Participants would view of the facilitators screen and when required view and interact with a separate webpage for the player DiBL screen. This “player” screen could be a separate tab or connected through another device.

Activity Design:

During the online sessions participants took part in three activities to foster discussion:

Activity 1 - Water Use Survey:

Figure 2: Image of facilitator screen (left) and player screen (right) during activity one, water use survey. On the player screen, participants can respond to a survey of questions before being shown the results of home water use on the player screen.

Content: Players are informed that they will be doing a survey to look at their water use. On the player screen a series of questions appear surveying current perceptions of water supply

within the UK and report on their daily water use habits to wash self, clean laundry, and wash dishes. Once the survey is completed, an estimate of daily water use is shown for each player. The results of this estimate can only be viewed on the player screen and so not shared with the group. This estimate is a point of reflection for the participants and used as a primer for thinking about water use and where we use water in daily life. Participants are invited to comment on their water use estimates.

Goal: Reflect on own water use and prime ideas of how individuals use water in their daily lives.

Data collected: Survey results on water supply perception and self-reported daily water use. Audio from discussions is recorded through the Zoom recordings which were later downloaded and transcribed. The survey data gives a benchmark on water perception and water use before other activities.

Figure 3: Flow of DiBL content and captured data for activity one – water use Survey. for the player DiBL screen. This “player” screen could be a separate tab or connected through another device.

Activity 2 – Data Exploration

Figure 4: Image of facilitator screen (left) and player screen (right) during activity two, data exploration. On the player screen, participants can view data and enter their response to the task given on the facilitator screen.

Content: Players are told that they will now look at some data and will need to create a title and tag line for a newspaper article that best describes this data. Two graphs are presented to the players on the facilitator screen where the facilitator breaks down the structure of the graphs (what do the numbers describe on the X and Y axis, what are lines / bars etc). This is to provide some data literacy to take on the activity. Players are then asked to verbally describe and discuss any part of these graphs to interpret water supply. After a discussion, players are asked to type in a title and tag line that best describes their interpretation of the graphs for a newspaper article on their player screen.

Goals: This activity is used to inform players of water supply and demand through data, give opportunity to ask questions within this domain, frame why water sustainability requires consideration, and foster ideas on water sustainability.

Data collected: Submitted ideas and voted upon favourite ideas are captured. Audio from discussions is recorded through the Zoom platform and later download and transcribed.

Figure 5: Flow of DiBL content and captured data for activity two – data exploration of supply and demand challenges.

Activity 3 – Save the City Dilemma Game

Content: Players are informed that they are now part of the task force HYDRO. Their mission is to maintain water supply with cities. They are then introduced to the town of Belton and how sufficient water enables personal use, essential services to run, and functioning commercial services. However, an emergency occurs when two summers of dry weather drives a water shortage. Both the facilitator screen and player screen are used to display media and information on this (newspaper article, city statistics). Players are informed that to save water, personal citizen use needs to reduce. Players are then given information on bathroom water use for the citizens of Belton, such as the format encountered in *Activity 1 – Water use Survey*. Players must halve water use in this area. Players then discuss how they can approach this and submit ideas through the player screen. These ideas are then voted upon. The favourite is put through a calculation page where the facilitator must give a green, amber, or red grading in the categories of “Washing Self”, “Flushing Toilet”, “Taps Running”, and “Public Acceptance”. Based on this calculation, three endings are possible. If little water is saved, then the city is still in dire need of water. If some good progress has been made, then the narrative highlights some more changes are needed. If enough water is saved, then narrative describes a happy city with water security. To bring this dilemma solution to the real world, the players are then shown what savings would be made if this plan was applied to the entire UK.

Figure 6: Image of facilitator screen (left) and player screen (right) during activity three, save the city dilemma game. On the player screen, participants can view citizen water use to start discussions on how this behaviour could be changed. The facilitator screen can give narrative information to prompt discussion context.

Goal: Share and discuss ideas on how citizens could waste less water, highlight that collective action can make a big difference in available water supply, and narratively connect water supply from the perspective of managing a city to individual citizen use.

Data Collected: Audio recordings gather ideas and opinions on how water can be saved. Areas of consensus and disagreement can be explored. Submitted ideas and voted ideas are recorded to highlight salient points that resonate with the players.

Figure 7: Flow of DiBL content and captured data for activity three – “Save the City” playful dilemma

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Activity 4 – Reflective Survey and Discussion

Figure 8: Image of facilitator screen (left) and player screen (right) during activity four, reflective survey. On the player screen, participants can respond to a survey of questions before group discussions occur based on points submitted that are shown on the facilitator screen.

Content: Players are told that the last activity is to reflect on their experience of the session. Through the player screen, participants are surveyed on their experience. Answers to the questions “What did you enjoy the least”, and “What did you enjoy the most” appear on the facilitators screen for general discussion within the group after the reflective survey is completed.

Goal: Gather reflective thoughts on the session momentarily after activity 3 has been completed.

Data Collected: Answers to the reflective survey are captured through the DiBL platform. Audio discussions were recorded through the Zoom platform. These recordings were later downloaded and transcribed.

Figure 9: Flow of DiBL content and captured data for activity four – reflective survey and discussion

3.2 Participant Selection

In total, across a pilot and main trial, 25 participants were recruited. For the pilot, a convenience sample was used from the University of Greater Manchester. For the trial, 19 participants took part across 5 online video session (female = 10, male = 9, mean age = 46, min age = 22, max age = 71). To recruit, a participant call was placed through the communication channels (e.g., LinkedIn, Facebook) of Waterwise. The call explained that we are exploring playful approaches to discussing water use. Through the sign-up process, participants were screened to make sure they were over 18 and living in the UK. No incentives were offered to participants in this study.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

Ethical consent was obtained for both the pilot (approval number: MANUAP00230) and the main trial (approval number: AUTOYEHP00356) through the University of Greater Manchester ethics committee. Participants were given an information sheet prior to taking part in the study and discussed at the beginning of the study sessions. The information sheet covered goals of the research, what would happen in the study session, what data would be gathered, and how this data would be stored and used. After being given time to read and ask questions on the information sheet, participants signed their consent to take part through an online survey.

3.4 Mapping of RQ's to Case Study:

Table 1. Mapping of research questions to the case study

Revised research objectives and questions	Simple formulation in terms of GREAT	Yes/No
RQ1. To understand how games-based activities can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How can GREAT be achieved?</i>	YES
RQ1.2 How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>Does GREAT do what we want it to do?</i>	YES
RQ1.3 How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How much work is it to use the GREAT approach?</i>	YES
RQ1.4 How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts?	<i>How widely applicable is what we do?</i>	NO
RQ2. To understand the benefits and risks to citizens, policy stakeholders and policy makers, of using games-based activities as a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ2.1 What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens' views in relation to social dilemmas.	<i>What is it about GREAT that makes it good for gathering and representing opinions and attitudes?</i>	YES

<p>RQ2.2 What are the benefits and risks to policy makers and policy stakeholders of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?</p>	<p><i>What is good and bad about GREAT for policy stakeholders and policy makers?</i></p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>RQ2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?</p>	<p><i>What is good and bad about GREAT for citizens?</i></p>	<p>YES</p>

3.4.1 Detail the design process for the case study:

The GCS2 case study and collaborative activities were developed using the GREAT project case study cycle (See figure 10). An overview of what took place at each step can be found in the following section.

Figure 10: GREAT Case Study Cycle (Stakeholder View). Taken from Hollins (2024), this diagram represents the 8 steps of collaboration to design, engage stakeholders, and advocate for policy changes through the GREAT project cycle.

Table 2. Detailing the design process for the case study

Step of Case Study Cycle	Overview of the Eight-Step Cycle <i>Provide a brief description of each step in the case study process.</i>
<p>Create and Prioritise Research Topics (Step 1) <i>Document the outcomes of initial workshops.</i></p>	<p>Through online meetings with representatives of Waterwise one potential policy and three themes emerged.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Water labelling policy 2) Awareness of water scarcity within the UK 3) How citizens can be nudged to less wasteful behaviour
<p>Collaborate in Study Design (Step 2) <i>Describe the collaborative case study design process.</i></p>	<p>General theme for playful activities were explored:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dilemmas focused on a world without water • Dilemmas focused on connecting individual water use with the broader system • Potential ideas for PlanetPlay survey (would you rather) • Aiming for a broad demographic, interested in people over 18 who pay for water.
<p>Collaborate in Design of Games-Based Activities (Step 3) <i>Explain the collaborative design of game activities.</i></p>	<p>Based on iterative meeting between Waterwise, SGI, and ZSI a flow for the DiBL was formed. This included a reflective water use survey, data exploration of water supply and demand challenges and a playful dilemma to discuss citizen water use.</p> <p>A pilot was conducted using a convenience sample (n = 6) to test timings and technology.</p>
<p>Piloting and Gathering Data (Step 4) <i>Document the piloting phase and data collection.</i></p>	<p>In total, 19 participants (female = 10, mean age = 46, min age = 22, max age = 71) were recruited for the main trial. Sessions took place between March and April 2025. Each session had 3-6 participants. All session discussions took place online through Zoom calls.</p> <p>Video sessions and transcriptions were recorded through Zoom features. Voting behaviour and text entry from the activities was captured through the DiBL platform.</p> <p>The water use survey for activity one was sent to participants one week later to compare perception of water in the UK and self-reporting of water use.</p>
<p>Data Interpretation and Outcomes (Step 5) <i>Analyse and interpret the data collected.</i></p>	<p>Data analysis was conducted using Reflexive Thematic Analysis:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reflection on Own Water Use 2. Awareness of UK Water Supply/Demand Challenges

	<p>3. Making Sense of Sustainable Water Use</p> <p>4. Critique of the Approach</p> <p>Comparison of survey in activity one and the same survey administered one week later was used to assess impact on self-reported water use, perception of water supply challenges, and changes in concern for water use.</p> <p>Implications: Bringing students and policymakers together for joint reflection on data was highly valuable and should be included in future case studies. Timing and ensuring active engagement remain challenges when working with schools, requiring careful planning.</p>
<p>Conclusions and Outputs (Step 6)</p> <p><i>Summarise conclusions and recommendations.</i></p>	<p>Summary of data analysis:</p> <p>Survey data:</p> <p>The water use survey reported a reduction in water use one week later, but this was not significant across the group. However, some individuals reported a large reduction in shower use and tap running</p> <p>It is likely that the approach nudged easy wins in individuals but not changes that require significant energy</p> <p>Participant perception of water security moved towards concern after sessions</p> <p>Participants felt they could better gauge the water they used</p> <p>Participants reported more attention on their water use after sessions</p> <p>Discussions Analysis:</p> <p>Survey and playful dilemma prompted more personal reflection than other activities</p> <p>Sensemaking of water sustainability occurred largely in playful dilemma</p> <p>Awareness of water supply challenges occurred mostly in data exploration activity</p> <p>Participants were more conscious of their water use after taking part in the zoom sessions</p>

	<p>SMART metering was seen as a good idea if it does not lead to punitive or micromanaged consequences. SMART metering was viewed as a positive tool to empower individuals with knowledge of their water use to then adjust behaviour.</p> <p>It was viewed positively to use SMART metering data to compare individual water use to the broader collective. Such data may help develop "water culture" and playful competition in reducing water waste</p> <p>Those that felt they were doing their part were concerned about visual signs that water companies are not looking after the infrastructure. If the public can see road-flooding leaks, then they are not going to spend energy and money on their own habits. There is work to be done on establishing a shared vision and responsibility between water infrastructure and public use. However, if SMART metering comes with an app, there are opportunities to communicate infrastructure efforts and local goals for water use.</p> <p>In general people liked the idea of water efficient devices but felt any upgrades are expensive. Without subsidies (or if part of a more general refurbishment), they would not be willing to spend money on water efficient hardware.</p> <p>Many liked the idea of recycling water. Rainwater was viewed as a missed opportunity. But no-one could articulate a plan on how this could be implemented which suggests a significant deficit of knowledge, but a potential popular water recycling approach.</p> <p>Critique of Approach</p> <p>Participants found the sessions positive</p> <p>Participants enjoyed interaction and story sharing</p> <p>Depth of sensemaking was largely limited to household habits. Although this was the aim of the discussion design, there is scope for more engagement with systemic dynamics.</p> <p>For those less technologically savvy on a mobile device found it frustrating to manage zoom and DiBL applications at the same time.</p>
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	<p>Recommendations:</p> <p>Clear instructions on using a desktop set up for these discussions.</p> <p>The practical home habits explored with this content should be bolstered by a commitment to making a small change to help consider actionable habits. If there is nothing to improve, this can be celebrated.</p> <p>Design of the DiBL means that different dilemmas can be used to cover a variety of sustainability topics. Scope to broaden discussion to systemic dynamics and policy areas.</p> <p>Across the activities, more playful design could be applied. Including individual goals and group goals to enhance mechanics of the discussion.</p>
<p>Public Engagement and Dissemination of Outcomes (Step 7) <i>Outline strategies for disseminating findings.</i></p>	<p>Published paper detailing design and impact of discussions on self-reported water use (Watson et al., 2025)</p> <p>Dissemination of case study and key insights through Waterwise newsletter and database for public view and within organisation view</p> <p>Ongoing scientific output in review for a JCAL special issue analysing the qualitative depth of water security discussions.</p> <p>Dissemination and outreach collaboration with EPIC-WE, a sister project. In this collaboration we used the GCS2 discussion activities to inspire game creation in a game jam. This included two cohorts of students taking part in the game jam at the University of Greater Manchester. Cohort 1 recruited international (to UK) students studying on a computer science masters course (n = 29). Cohort 2 recruited undergraduate students studying on a games course (n = 24). This additionally resulted in a collaborative paper submission with EPIC-WE currently under review for Foundations in Game 2026 conference.</p>
<p>Advocate for Change at Policy Level (Step 8) <i>Document advocacy efforts undertaken.</i></p>	<p>Work within this phase of the case study was viewed positively by our sponsor Waterwise. One insight was discussed as important but required further investigation. It was agreed that a second iteration of the case study should be conducted to quantitatively explore broader opinions on rainwater harvesting as this might have implications for building regulations that are under discussion.</p>

4. SWOT Analysis of Case Study Methodology

Table 3. SWOT analysis of the case study methodology

Strengths <i>Examine the strengths of the case study methodology, such as the use of innovative data collection techniques (e.g., game-based activities, surveys) or high participant engagement levels.</i>	Weaknesses <i>Identify any methodological limitations encountered, such as sample size constraints or challenges in capturing a full range of participant perspectives.</i>
<p>Rich discussions that show breadth across water supply and use within the home</p> <p>Engagement with sustainability knowledge & practice is evident through participant inquiry</p> <p>The DiBL has been received as positive and engaging with many viewing the interaction between participants as a strength</p> <p>Short duration of DiBL means it can be applied in citizen friendly context. Modular design suggests content can change depending on focus of discussions</p> <p>DiBL shown to be effective for online discussions, which can be a challenging space.</p> <p>Some evidence of behaviour changes with water habits</p>	<p>More depth of discussion and co-constructed outcomes would require greater focus within tasks and discussion topic</p> <p>Requires broader participation from a variety of demographics to parse views and perspectives on local concerns as well as broader sustainability responsibilities.</p> <p>Potential for social desirability bias in survey response and discussions</p>
Opportunities <i>Highlight areas for potential development, such as refining the methodology, expanding participant demographics, or exploring future research collaborations to enhance insights.</i>	Threats <i>Identify external challenges that may impact the study's success, such as resource limitations, data access issues, or potential resistance from stakeholders.</i>
<p>Opportunity to combine core activities from DiBL into one game for a more seamless, playful experience.</p> <p>This approach was conducted online and so there is opportunity to explore in person formats (classroom, social, and workroom activity spaces). Potential to link this DiBL work with Planet Play survey data.</p>	<p>Impact of work requires objective measurement of water use which is impractical to get currently.</p> <p>Policy engagement form data collected requires interpretation form this work. Requires data points that bridge the gap between policy and sustainability behaviour</p>

5. Key Findings

For the context of this report, the key findings are discussed in relation to the GREAT project research questions.

RQ 1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?

Three activities were used to foster discussion on water sustainability behaviours and supporting knowledge of water supply systems; a survey which with immediate representation of behaviour, a data exploration activity, and a social dilemma game.

Survey with immediate representation of behaviour

Although not a game, the survey engaged participants with their water behaviour through real-time calculations. Participants immediately saw their estimated water use for washing, laundry, and dishes. While engagement wasn't formally evaluated, verbal and written responses suggested participants were surprised by their consumption levels. As a reflective technique, the survey appeared effective, the calculations helped frame water volumes that are otherwise difficult to imagine, structuring subsequent discussions. However, the survey generated the fewest discussions, likely because it came first (creating nervousness about sharing personal habits) and required silent completion (creating awkward pauses). For eliciting views on social dilemmas, this approach proved ineffective. But for self-reflection and framing discussions, it shows potential as a primer for water sustainability conversations.

Game Design Improvements: This survey could be enhanced through character development. Participant responses could generate player STATS and roles for subsequent activities. Audio and visual feedback, such as water filling the screen as questions are answered, could increase engagement. Water use calculations could assign monikers to players (e.g., "Water Saver", "Heavy User") to enable group comparison. Ideas of gamification could be utilised to show player water use compared to a demographic average or represent the water use within a *leaderboard of sustainability*.

Data Exploration

Exploring water supply and demand data successfully prompted discussion. Participants answered questions directly from the data or drew on personal knowledge to interpret it, fostering learning and debate. Many reported better understanding the supply-demand tension and appreciated seeing actual data, highlighting this approach's educational potential. The data was sufficiently accessible, participants could comment and interpret without exceeding their

data literacy. The challenge lay in creating newspaper titles from the data. Some participants noted difficulty combining interpretation with creativity under time pressure, although most still submitted titles. Voting on favourites engaged participants by showcasing peer work, with gold trophies awarded to top entries.

This method effectively elicited and communicated views on the data and underlying social dilemmas. Discussions addressed tensions between infrastructure supply, storage, and sectoral use. The macro-level framing sparked debate beyond household consumption, participants raised concerns about industrial water use (data centres) and how infrastructure leakage unfairly shifts blame to citizens. The activity thus revealed citizen perspectives on both system-citizen relationships and inter-sectoral dynamics (infrastructure, power generation, etc.).

Game Design Improvements: This activity builds shared narratives from data that could set the scene for subsequent games or dilemma scenarios, for example, estimating sectoral water volumes using relatable metrics (cars, bins, swimming pools). To reduce the creative burden, players could assemble titles from provided words or complete fill-in-the-blank headlines.

Social Dilemma Game – Save the City

The goal of halving water use within the dilemma narrative effectively prompted discussions on citizen behaviour (daily water use) and supporting infrastructure (meters, messaging). Participants suggested behavioural changes, crafted messaging strategies, considered demographic impacts, shared experiences, and built on each other's ideas. However, water's ubiquity in daily life allowed discussions to drift off-topic, and participants with sustainability expertise sometimes dominated conversations with personal preferences. While the approach successfully elicited attitudes and preferences, achieving depth required focus and skilled facilitation to ensure all voices were heard. The activity concluded with participants submitting plans for facilitator review. This synthesised discussions but didn't enhance view elicitation or representation. In larger groups, such mechanisms would capture broader input, but in small discussion groups it proved unnecessary and drained energy at session's end. The game demonstrates that a clear narrative and goal are sufficient to generate discussion and develop shared understanding of water waste.

Activity	Discussion Summary
1: Survey	Reflection on own water use occurred with inquisition on water volumes. Reflection was vocalised at a surface level with interest in how results might compare to known averages.
2: Data Exploration	Inquiry into what drives water distribution was common with an effort to interpret why sectors may be increasing in water use (data centres). Discussions were more easily framed at a system level. Concern about water supply was also present as well as acknowledgement that public water use is a significant “chunk” of freshwater reserves.
3: Save the City - Dilemma	Discussions focused on sensemaking of sustainable water use. What water habits could be reduced, and what supportive measures might help this. A wide-ranging discussion that drew from individuals’ water stories and knowledge. Reflection on own water use was also present as well as empathy to the needs of different demographics.

Table 4. Overview of discussion content for each activity highlighting the impact on conversation content

Game Design Improvements: The dilemma game highlights how narrative can frame a discussion. This can be improved with more expressive media such as a video or small interactions (sliders to move or flipping over panels to reveal information) within the narrative given. To help discussion, the information provided to the players could be more interactive. Utilise sliders to show impact of changing behaviours on a final score. This draws on the immediate feedback that engages players with games and reduces cognitive load on working out the impact of a given plan. Information from these sliders could then be captured and voted upon to reduce the need for excessive writing at the end of a discussion session. The second game design element to refine would be to assign objectives or tasks for each player. Creating individual tasks and shared objectives. This would allow for a greater variety of mechanics to aid discussions. The difficulty would be to not over burden the players to maintain energy.

RQ 1.2 How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens’ views on social dilemmas?

The activities provided opportunities to learn about water supply and the relationship between citizen use and societal needs. The DiBL platform's multimedia capabilities helped visualise data and sustainability contexts, fostering learning through both presented information and group discussion. This knowledge development framed the sustainability issue, enabling participants to express and discuss views within a shared context.

The dilemma game demonstrated that a clear scenario and goal are sufficient to generate focused discussion. Participants articulated views on individual water behaviours and infrastructure solutions within the scenario. There is the question of breadth vs depth in these discussions. The sessions were an hour long and so limited time could be given to such discussions. The myriad of ways that water is integrated into daily life means that discussion can move off topic. This is not necessarily a negative aspect as citizens will need space and time to grapple with the complexities of sustainable issues, but it may mean that depth of discussion is curtailed due to the limited time. While this exploration may help citizens grapple with sustainability complexities, it curtailed depth. More focused dilemmas could sharpen discussion.

Since activities emphasised group discussion, participants may have offered socially desirable responses or withheld input due to lack of confidence in a new group. Facilitators worked to enable agreement, dissent, and inclusive participation. This issue might diminish in groups with established relationships or discussing locally relevant dilemmas.

A follow up survey was conducted one week after the discussion sessions. Individuals reported being more conscious about their water use with some identifying behaviour change (reduction in showers, turning off taps). However, no significant impact on reported water behaviour across the group was observed. Results suggest small effect sizes on some participants, though without independent observation, findings rely on self-reported accuracy.

Some participants struggled with DiBL player interactions and Zoom displays, particularly on mobile devices. Most issues were resolved through guidance, but some initially wanted to withdraw from activities due to these barriers. This highlights the tension between accessibility (enabling nationwide participation) and usability (ensuring most participants can navigate the platform).

Figure 11: Bar charts adapted from Watson (2025), showing the agreement response (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree) to Likert questions from the survey administered in activity 1 and the follow-up survey one week after the activities. Participants showed greater confidence in estimating own water use and showed more agreement that changes are required to maintain water security.

RQ 1.3 How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?

Developing playful, interactive activities that elicit citizen attitudes and preferences is time-consuming. Tensions exist between eliciting conversations and instilling fun, and between stakeholder needs. Compromising between these actors and designing effective tools requires significant time for design, configuration, and testing. Multiple iterations are likely needed to refine tools for broader audiences. This is unsurprising, but the GREAT approach provides a structured framework with clear steps and milestones to navigate these tensions and foster progress. For this case study, progressing from initial conversations to the first main trial took 10 months, longer than expected. Given this investment, design approaches should be transparently documented so others can build upon the work using their chosen technology.

Regarding discussion sessions, attitudes and preferences on social dilemmas were elicited with communal sensemaking and debate within an hour. The playful format efficiently captured

individual and group perspectives within a reasonable timeframe, though longer sessions might deepen discussions.

Figure 12: Bar chart highlighting the diverse topics discussed in the playful dilemma activity to reduce wasteful water use.

RQ 2.1 What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens’ views in relation to social dilemmas.

Although modern games employ numerous engagement elements, we leveraged a playful narrative and clear goal to engage participants with water use as a social dilemma. This approach elicited attitudes and preferences within groups of strangers. Slight modifications to narrative, participant responsibility, and goals could explore the same dilemma from various perspectives and problem domains, suggesting that playful approaches afford structured spaces where many feel comfortable sharing knowledge and stories.

Such spaces enable individuals to share, learn, and test their thoughts. When options were presented, group responses were largely constructive with minimal dissent. This suggests participants avoided confrontation, potentially withholding disagreement and biasing towards positive opinions. Game design conversation mechanics could draw out dissent by rewarding debate alongside consensus.

Many viewed the discussion spaces positively, highlighting member interaction as their favourite element, suggesting that discussion itself is engaging. The playful dilemma and supporting activities provided opportunities to explore personal water use and share thoughts, stories, and views. The underlying platform technology captured attitudes and preferences through discussion, voting behaviour, and text entry, enabling analysis from varied participant input.

RQ 2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?

Risks to participants were minimal in this case study. Neither participation nor post-discussion impact would likely affect individuals negatively. Many viewed their experience positively, directly commenting that they learnt about the water system and their own water use, and found peer interactions interesting. Some reported behaviour change, though limited to low effort shifts (turning taps off, shorter showers). This suggests benefits are educational, reflective, social, and may heighten concern for individual behaviours.

Time presents the greatest barrier. Volunteering an hour for such discussions may be excessive for the public. To overcome this, the approach would need to align with existing schedules and integrate into educational or workplace sessions and seminars.

Data Gaps

Data on impact of discussions on water use behaviour relies on a self-reported survey. This reporting is important but if data of actual water use could be gathered, then this would better identify the impact on individuals. Data gathered is qualitative and demographics do not represent a generalisable population. Within this group there is a bias towards positive view on water sustainability as such people are likely to volunteer to take part in these activities.

Broader quantitative data on any highlighted themes from this phase of the case study would help validate findings as well as provide opportunity for more detail within these themes.

6. Policy Implications and Recommendations

SMART metres appear an acceptable infrastructure approach. Messaging should emphasise how they empower understanding of personal water use and leak detection. There was some interest in seeing own stats against others if the resolution of the data kept it anonymous

Water companies should strongly communicate infrastructure and service improvements. Citizens are less likely to resent behavioural changes if they perceive industry is also reducing waste.

Improving water efficiency of devices requires financial support. The carrot of a more sustainable future is not strong enough for citizens to save the money required for these changes. Relying on citizen willingness to update water hardware will have minimal effect unless costs are perceived as reasonable or risks are clearly highlighted.

Reducing shower time appears attainable, and some participants had not considered running taps wasteful until shown the volume wasted. Demonstrating this waste at individual and collective scales, alongside practical solutions (reminder stickers), may encourage reduced usage in these areas.

Messaging around health benefits (fewer showers benefit skin and hair) with water reduction as a secondary benefit resonated well with some participants.

There is a general lack of knowledge of how the water system works within the UK. For example, where do we abstract water from and what impacts these stores. There appears to be heightened confusion with the understanding that climate change should mean warmer, wetter climate in the UK. Raising questions about why water reserves are diminishing. Re-visiting the water cycle within the context of how water is stored geographically may help framework the need for sustainable water practices and policies.

Water recycling and rainwater use were viewed very positively. However, respondents lacked clarity on implementation details. This suggests public support for diverse water sources exists, although the strength of this support remains uncertain without clearer understanding. Still, it presents an opportunity to engage citizens on practical approaches.

7. Conclusion

We engaged participants with three activities to spark online discussions and sensemaking of UK water security: a reflective survey on water use, data exploration of supply-demand challenges, and a playful dilemma to save a city from drought. Using the DiBL platform, we observed how this approach elicited stories, discussions, text entry, and voting on water sustainability. Although no significant group-level impact on water use behaviour was found, individuals reported substantial reductions. One week later, participants reported greater concern for their water use, but this did not encourage further discussion with others.

Participants found the experience positive and enjoyed the discussion interaction. Despite some difficulties balancing video conferencing and DiBL screens on mobile devices, the approach effectively generated online discussion.

Participants valued empowerment over personal water use and local decision-making. SMART metering was viewed favourably, provided it avoided punitive or micromanaged consequences. Those perceiving themselves as responsible felt frustrated by visible signs of neglected infrastructure, road-flooding leaks signal that water companies aren't maintaining systems. If the public sees such waste, they're unlikely to invest energy and money in personal habits. Work is needed to establish shared vision and responsibility between infrastructure providers and the public. However, if SMART metering includes an app, opportunities exist to communicate infrastructure efforts and local water use goals.

Generally, people favoured water-efficient devices but considered upgrades expensive. Without subsidies (or integration into broader refurbishments), they wouldn't invest in water-efficient hardware. Many favoured water recycling, viewing rainwater as a missed opportunity. However, no one articulated implementation plans, suggesting significant knowledge deficits despite potential popularity for water recycling approaches.

7.1 Future Directions

To build upon the work done in this phase of the case study we recommend:

Theme Expansion: The activities revealed themes meriting deeper exploration, particularly policies encouraging less wasteful water behaviour. Participants strongly supported water recycling and harvesting yet understanding of how these practices operate in everyday settings was limited. Whether this positive perception would persist once costs and maintenance requirements are explicit remains unclear. Participants also responded well to tools increasing

awareness of personal water use. Simple mechanisms enabling individuals to compare usage with their immediate community may offer an accessible route to fostering reflective, sustainable water practices.

Game Design: The trialled activities have clear potential for development into game-based experiences. Incorporating interactive data, structured discussion roles, and water use surveys could support experimentation with discussion based and non-discussion based engagement modes. This would enable exploration of how players understand their own water use and situate themselves within the wider water system.

Refine Current Content: The existing content effectively stimulates online discussion. Testing it in additional contexts, in-person workshops or educational seminars, would assess relevance across different demographics and settings. The thematic focus could also address a broader set of social dilemmas related to water security, extending the approach's applicability.

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